

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10822511>

DEVELOPMENT OF SPORTS ACTIVITY IN STUDENTS, TAKING INTO ACCOUNT THEIR INDIVIDUALITY.

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ANNOTATION

Today, physical education classes in higher educational institutions are an important part of strengthening the health of the younger generation. Physical education teachers use various forms, methods and means to make classes more interesting and interesting but often they encounter some problems that can lead to various complications during the educational process. This article reveals a study of sports activity among students, taking into account their individuality.

Key words: *sports activity, individuality, personality, students, independence.*

The individuality of a person is not some completely exclusive and immanently inherent purely biological, innate property, independent of living conditions and upbringing. B. M. Teplov emphasized that “no psychological feature of a person is determined only by the properties of the nervous system. It is always the result of education in the broad sense of the word but for some children, life opportunities in general and educational opportunities in particular fall on one basis (certain properties of the nervous system), for others, on another.”

Personality is formed under the influence of interactions and relationships, which also influence other people and therefore contribute to the formation of some common, typical social-class and socio-psychological traits. A number of typical psychological characteristics of students allows us to combine them into conditional groups. In turn, identifying typical groups of student-athletes will help coaches and teachers more purposefully influence the student’s personality, without isolating him from the team and the relationships in which he is located. The main criterion by which student-athletes are divided into groups is the need of students for sports activities and the presence of relevant experience in its implementation. Identification of the characteristics of groups makes it possible to determine the trend in the development of activity in sports activities of both the team and the individual of each student.

Group I - students with a pronounced interest in sports activities and the presence of skills to satisfy this need. The main task of a trainer-teacher is to give students a new field of sports activity, quite complex, but at the same time feasible, using the skills and abilities they have already acquired. As a rule, this group is small, it includes the best student-athletes, but they need to be worked with and an individual approach is required.

Group II - students with a pronounced desire for sports activities who do not have the skills to implement this desire. When working with such teenagers, it is advisable for a trainer-teacher to show ways that would help them take a leading place in the team, teach them how to perform sports exercises, combinations, and techniques well.

Group III students show interest only in individual sports combinations and techniques, but not in sports activities in general and do not have sufficient skills to implement them. The main task of the trainer-teacher: using the interests and inclinations, knowledge and skills of students, gradually bring them to satisfaction with participation in sports activities, including combinations of varying complexity in the exercise system.

Group IV - students do not show much interest in sports activities and do not have certain skills in its implementation. When working with students in this most difficult group, it is advisable for the trainer-teacher to identify and neutralize the reasons for their negative attitude towards sports, so that they can contribute to the active sports activities of the entire team. In this regard, it is necessary to set before students of this group in the process of sports activities both general collective tasks and individual ones in relation to each student.

When organizing students' sports activities, the coach-teacher must be guided by the principle of the unity of consciousness and activity. Involving students in sports activities begins with relying on the student's desire to master a specific sport. But a student will be able to master even a sport that is interesting to him only by accumulating certain skills and experience in performing a number of specific, sometimes quite complex exercises and combinations. Therefore, when organizing sports activities, one must also pay attention to the student's internal position, which changes depending on the degree of interest in specific methods, methods of performing sports exercises, the availability of skills and experience in mastering the technical and tactical techniques of a particular sport, relationships in the team and group. Relying on the student's existing interests allows him to form and develop new ones, gradually expanding the scope of his interested participation in sports activities. Thus, activities of interest should be considered as an important means of including a teenager in the diverse sports activities of a team, as an opportunity to shape his individuality and cultivate a harmoniously developed personality.

The content of students' sports activities at the initial stage depends on their belonging to one or another designated group. For example, when work with students of group I, you can start by transferring the acquired sports knowledge and skills to other team members, students are active assistants to the trainer-teacher in organizing training and sports instructors. With students of group II, one should begin with the accumulation of experience in performing and organizing sports activities. The forms of work in one group are also different, since the activity of adolescents when participating in certain types of sports activities is different. The variety of forms and types of sports work with student-athletes creates favorable conditions for their inclusion in those types of activities that best suit their individual characteristics. The division of students into groups has only a relative, methodological significance. Groups are not static. In the process of educational work, student-athletes constantly move from group to group towards a higher level of sports skill.

Analysis of the results of the study showed the following: 1 the initial characteristics of students' attitudes towards sports activities vary from initiative, independence, diligence to non-participation in activities and even creating obstacles for others 2 the process of developing sports activity in most students proceeds spasmodically, which is explained not only by the psychological characteristics of age and individual capabilities, but also a selective attitude towards sports activities. Increasing the activity of adolescents in sports activities is primarily associated with achieving high sports results.

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